

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

W8013S, a promising thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) line for two-line system hybrid rice breeding

Zhang Xianguang and Lu Xingguo, Food Crops Research Institute, Hubei Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Wuhan 430064 China

W6154S, which is thermosensitive, was derived from the original Hubei photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile rice Nong Ken 58S. The fertility of W6154S can be greatly altered by temperature variation during fertility induction. Its use in hybrid seed production is therefore limited.

We tried to breed new TGMS lines that have lower critical temperature for fertility restoration than W6154S (25.2 ± 1.0 °C). W8013S is such a TGMS line.

W8013S, derived from the cross W6154S/Xie Qing Zhao//Xie Qing Zhao, has japonica-type cytoplasm and indica-type nuclear background. It is photoperiod-insensitive (see table).

W8013S flowers in Wuhan 58-93 d (CV = 8.6%) after a late Mar to late Jul sowing. It has a mean cumulative effective temperature of 1244.6 °C (CV = 11.0%)

We observed that the stable male sterile period in W8013S was from 2 Jul to 16 Sep. During this period, a 99.5–100% abortive pollen rate and almost zero seed-setting rate under natural light/temperature conditions occurred. Day length or theoretical light length (12–14 h) affects its sterility very little.

Correlation analysis was made on the abortive pollen rate at heading and each of the nine temperature components including daily air temperature, water temperature, and soil temperatures at 0, 5, 10, and 20 cm beneath the surface 7–22 d before heading.

The most closely correlated component was the soil surface temperature occurring 12-16 d before heading. This means that the thermosensitive stage in W8013S

Fertility test and analysis of fertility response in TGMS lines. Wuhan, China, 1990.

Material	Abortive pollen rate ^a (%)			Type	Thermosensitive stage ^b	<i>r</i> value ^c	Index of critical temperature (°C)
	LD	SD	<i>t</i>				
W6154S	99.69	98.97	1.67	TGMS	12–15	0.507–0.707**	25.2 ± 1.0
W8013S	99.36	98.86	0.79	TGMS	12–16	0.556–0.746**	24.4 ± 0.9
W6111S	99.90	99.88	0.20	TGMS	11–14	0.775–0.835**	25.5 ± 1.1
NK58S (check)	99.98	27.93	12.57*	PGMS			

^a LD = 16 h light + 8 h dark. SD = 10 h light + 14 h dark. Treatments were from the midstage of the first rachis-branch primordium differentiation to heading; mean air temperature ranged from 26.6 to 30.5°C. ^b The *i*th day before heading. ^c ** = significant difference at P < 0.01.

remains when the pollen mother cells undergo meiosis. By doing further regression analysis using the abortive pollen rate of 99.5–100% as the eligible index, we obtained a critical temperature (24.4 ± 0.9°C) for its fertility alteration (see table). The index is obviously lower than that for W6154S and other TGMS lines.

Higher temperature (*t* ³ 25.3°C) induces completely sterile pollens; lower temperature (*t* = 23.0–25.2°C) induces

fertile ones. Lower critical temperature is necessary for producing hybrid seed during the higher temperature seasons. The extremely low temperatures in mid-summer 1989 were a good test for stability. W6154S and some other TGMS lines became partially fertile, but W8013S was still highly sterile.

Extensive testcrossing of indica and japonica varieties and screening of F₁ crosses are under way to exploit the breeding potential of W8013S. □

Buli-INIA, the first fine-grain rice variety released in Chile

J. R. Alvarado and P. Grau, Quilamapu Experiment Station-National Institute for Agricultural Research (INIA), Chillan, Chile; C. P. Martinez and E. Pulver, International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), Rice Program, Cali, Colombia

Low temperatures at seedling and flowering stages are a major constraint in rice production in Chile. Japonica rice, such as Oro and Quila, with bold, short or medium grains and a high degree of white belly has traditionally been grown in Chile. But consumer

preference is changing.

INIA released Diamante in 1979. It has long, translucent grain, but its eating quality did not meet the new standards of Chilean consumers who prefer high-quality imported rices, such as Bluebelle.

INIA and CIAT began a collaborative research project in 1984 to develop germplasm that combines cold tolerance, earliness, and good grain quality. Buli-INIA, a semidwarf with translucent, long, slender grain, is the first variety to come from the joint venture. It was selected from a cross between Lemont/Quila 66304 and Diamante. Both Quila 66304 and Diamante are early and cold tolerant.

Some agronomic and grain characteristics and yield of Buli-INIA and check varieties from regional trial data during 3 growing seasons (1988–91) in Chile.

	Plant ht (cm)	Days to flowering ^a	Milled rice				Yield (t/ha)		
			Length: width	White belly ^b	1,000-grain wt (g)	Amylose ^c (%)	1988–89	1989–90	1990–91
Buli-INIA	82–97	96–124	3.3	0.2–0.8	26.0	20.6	7.0	5.6	7.1
Diamante-INIA	89–114	93–118	2.9	0.4–1.0	33.0	21.6	7.9	6.1	6.8
Oro	97–103	84–115	1.7	4.2–4.8	32.0	20.6	8.3	6.2	6.7
Quila-INIA	84–115	84–115	1.8	1.4–4.3	30.0	20.6	7.0	6.7	6.4

^a Dependent on planting date. ^b Scored on scale of 0 to 5: 0 = clear, translucent grain, 5 = chalky grain. ^c Determined in IRRRI laboratory.

Lemont has excellent grain quality.

Buli-INIA showed yield potential similar to that of check varieties in 13 regional trials in Chile during 1988-89 (see table).

Its growth duration is similar to Diamante's, but it has better tillering ability, shorter and stronger stems, a grain length:width > 3. and lower 1,000-grain weight.

Buli-INIA is resistant to lodging and tolerates low temperature (15-17 °C) better than Diamante and Oro. Head rice recovery is about 50%, eating quality is good.

V18, a promising new rice variety for the Red River Delta of Vietnam

N. T. Tuyen and D. T. Tuan, Plant Physiology Department, Vietnam Agricultural Science institute (INSA), Hanoi, Vietnam

V18 is a promising, high-yielding, semidwarf rice (95-105 cm) with a high photosynthetic rate and high response to N. It was developed at INSA from IR8/Lomello/Lao Tim.

V18 matures in 180–185 d in dry season and 130–135 d in wet season. It has very good plant type: moderate tillering, late senescence, and erect, dark green leaves.

Grains are medium-size, translucent, and have good cooking quality. The 1,000-grain weight is 27g. High percentages of ripened grains, total milled rice, and head rice recovery characterized V18.

V18 has good seedling cold tolerance and is moderately resistant to major pests and diseases. It yielded 17% more than

Table 1. Performance of V18 in replicated yield trials in 1985-88 dry seasons.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (103/m ²)	Ripened grains (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Milling recovery (%)	Head rice (%)
<i>With 100 kg N/ha</i>							
V18	6.2	277	23	86	27	72	53
IR8	5.8	248	21	81	28	68	33
<i>With 200 kg N/ha</i>							
V18	7.5	311	28	85	27	-	-
IR8	6.4	288	23	75	28	-	-

Table 2. Performance of V18 at Dan phuong-Hanoi and Mo lao-Ha son binh, Vietnam, 1988-90 dry seasons.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)				Increase (%)
	1988	1989	1990	Mean	
<i>Dan phuong</i>					
V18	5.3 (4.6)	6.4 (10)	6.1 (40)	6.1	13.3
IR8 (check)	4.1 (180)	5.8 (5.4)	5.7 (0.7)	5.4	
<i>Mo lao</i>					
V18		6.1 (7.2)	6.4 (18)	6.2	21.6
V14 (check)		5.0 (20)	5.3 (15)	5.1	

^a Figures in parentheses indicate area in ha.

check variety IR8 in research trials and 13.3–21.6% more in farmers' fields (Table 1, 2).

V18 was released for use in the highly

fertile soils of the Red River Delta. It is being tested on an estimated 1,000 ha in the delta. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

VL Dhan 221, a new upland rice variety for the northwestern Himalayan region of India

R. K. Sharma, V. S. Chauhan, K. D. Koranne, J. C. Bhatt, D. K. Garg and H. C. Joshi, Vivekanandu Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala (ICAR), Almora 263601, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

Rice variety VL Dhan 221 was released in 1991 for upland kharif cultivation in UP and Himachal Pradesh (HP). Derived from IR2053/Ch 1039, VL Dhan 221 was developed through the pedigree method at ICAR from IRRI material.

VL Dhan 221 was tested in All India Coordinated Trials conducted at different sites in UP and HP. It yielded an average of 2.5 t/ha, 28.8% more than national check Bala and 31.5% more than the best qualifying genotype HPU2202 (Table 1).

VL Dhan 221 is semitall with compact and well-exserted panicles, good spikelet fertility, and awnless medium grains. It

matures in 110-115 d, tillers well, tolerates drought and low temperature fairly well, and resists leaf and neck blast and stem borer (Table 2).

Rice under rainfed upland conditions in UP hills was traditionally sown during Mar-Apr and remained in the field until Sep. Only three crops (spring rice - wheat - finger millet - fallow) could

Table 1. Yield performance of VL Dhan 221 in coordinated trials.^a UP and HP, India, 1985-87.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)				Superiority (%)
	1985 (4)	1986 (3)	1987 (4)	Av yield	
VL Dhan 221	2.9	2.8	1.7	2.5	
Bala (check)	2.2	2.2	1.4	1.9	28.8
HPU2202	2.4	2.3	1.1	1.9	31.5

^a Figures in parentheses indicate number of locations.